

The text in panels has the first twenty-one verses of the poem in parise of Tārā without the coda. Here we give the full text as this is transmitted in both Tibetan and Sanskrit texts together:

༄༅། །ཉུ་གར་སྐད་དུ། །ཡུ་རྩ་དེ་མན་དུ་སྤྲུལ་སྤྲོད་མ་སྐྱེ་དེ་ཀའི་ཤཉི་ཀརྱ་མ། །བོད་སྐད་དུ།
 །འཕགས་མ་སྤྲོལ་མའི་ཙ་བའི་སྤྲུགས་ཀྱིས་བསྐྱོད་ཅིང་ཕྱག་འཚལ་བ་ཉི་ཤུ་ཙག་ཙག་ཞེས་བྱ་
 །བ། །ཨོ་ཇེ་བཙུན་མ་འཕགས་མ་སྤྲོལ་མ་ཕྱག་འཚལ་ལོ།

།ཕྱག་འཚལ་སྤྲོལ་མ་སྤྲུར་མ་དཔའ་མོ།
 །སྤྲོན་ནི་སྐད་ཙག་སྤྲོག་དང་འབྲ་མ།
 །འཇིག་རྟེན་གསུམ་མགོན་ཚུ་སྐྱེས་ཞལ་གྱི།
 །གེ་སར་བྱེ་བ་ལས་ནི་བྱང་མ།།༡

།ཕྱག་འཚལ་སྤྲོན་ཀའི་ཟླ་བ་ཀུན་དུ།
 །གང་བ་བརྒྱ་ནི་བཙུགས་པའི་ཞལ་མ།
 །སྐར་མ་སྤོང་ཕྱག་ཚོགས་པ་རྣམས་ཀྱི།
 །རབ་དུ་ཕྱེ་བའི་འོད་རབ་འབར་མ།།༢

།ཕྱག་འཚལ་སེར་སྤྲོ་ཚུ་ནས་སྐྱེས་ཀྱི།
 །པལྒས་ཕྱག་ནི་རྣམ་པར་བརྒྱན་མ།
 །སྤྲོན་པ་བཙུན་འགྲུས་དཀའ་ཐུབ་ཞེ་བ།
 །བཟོད་པ་བསམ་གཏན་སྤྲོད་ཡུལ་ཉིད་མ།།༣

།ཕྱག་འཚལ་དེ་བཞིན་གཤེགས་པའི་གཙུག་གཏོ་ད།
 །མཐའ་ཡས་རྣམ་པར་རྒྱལ་བར་སྤྲོད་མ།

|མ་ལུས་པ་རྩོལ་ཕྱིན་པ་ཐོབ་པའི།

|རྒྱལ་བའི་སྲས་ཀྱིས་ཤིན་ཏུ་བསྟེན་མཁོ།།༥

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་དུ་རྩེ་ར་རྩྱི་ཡི་གེས།

|འདྲོད་དང་སྦྱོགས་དང་ནམ་མཁའ་གང་མ།

|འཇིག་རྟེན་བདུན་པོ་ཞབས་ཀྱིས་མནན་ཏེ།

|ལུས་པ་མེད་པར་འགྲུགས་པར་རྒྱས་མཁོ།།༥

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་བརྒྱ་བྱིན་མེ་ལྷ་ཚངས་པ།

|རླུང་ལྷ་སྣ་ཚོགས་དབང་ཕྱག་མཚོད་མ།

|འབྲུང་པོ་རོ་ལངས་རྩི་བ་རྣམས་དང།

|གནོད་སྦྱིན་ཚོགས་ཀྱིས་མདུན་ནས་བསྟོད་མཁོ།།༥

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་དུ་ར་ཅེས་བྱ་དང་ཕའ་ཀྱིས།

|པ་རྩོལ་འཕྲུལ་འཁོར་རབ་དུ་འཇོམས་མ།

|གཡས་བསྐྱུམས་གཡོན་བརྒྱུངས་ཞབས་ཀྱིས་མནན་ཏེ།

|མེ་འབར་འབྲུག་པ་ཤིན་ཏུ་འབར་མཁོ།།༥

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་དུ་ར་འཇིགས་པ་ཆེན་པོ།

|བདུད་ཀྱི་དཔའ་བོ་རྣམ་པར་འཇོམས་མ།

|རྩྱེས་ཞལ་ཞི་ཁྲོ་གཉེར་ལྷན་མཇོད།

|དག་བོ་ཐམས་ཅད་མ་ལུས་གསོད་མཁོ།།༥

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་དུ་ཀོན་མཚོག་གསུམ་མཚོན་ཕྱག་རྒྱའི།

|སོར་མོས་ཐུགས་ཀར་རྣམ་པར་བརྒྱན་མ།

|མ་ལུས་ཕྱོགས་ཀྱི་འཁོར་ལོས་བརྒྱན་པའི།

|རང་གི་འོད་ཀྱི་ཚོགས་རྣམས་འབྲུགས་མ།།༩

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་རབ་དུ་དགའ་བ་བརྗོད་པའི།

|དབུ་རྒྱན་འོད་ཀྱི་སྤང་བ་སྤེལ་མ།

|བཞད་པ་རབ་བཞད་དུ་རྫོ་ར་ཡིས།

|བདུད་དང་འཇིག་རྟེན་དབང་དུ་མཛད་མ།།༡༠

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་ས་གཞི་སྐྱོང་བའི་ཚོགས་རྣམས།

|ཐམས་ཅད་འགྲུགས་པར་རུས་མ་ཉིད་མ།

|ཁྲོ་གཉེར་གཡོ་བའི་ཡི་གེ་རྩྱུ་གིས།

|སྤོངས་པ་ཐམས་ཅད་རྣམ་པར་སྐྱོལ་མ།།༡༡

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་ཟླ་བའི་དུམ་བུས་དབུ་བརྒྱན།

|བརྒྱན་པ་ཐམས་ཅད་ཤིན་དུ་འབར་མ།

|རལ་པའི་ཁྲོད་ན་འོད་དཔག་མེད་ལས།

|རྟག་པར་ཤིན་དུ་འོད་རབ་མཛད་མ།།༡༢

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་བསྐྱལ་པའི་ཐ་མའི་མེ་ལྷ་ར།

|འབར་བའི་སྤང་བའི་དབུས་ན་གནས་མ།

|གཡས་བརྒྱུངས་གཡོན་བསྐྱམས་ཀུན་ནས་བསྐྱོར་དགའི།

|དབྱ་ཡི་དཔུང་ནི་རྣམ་པར་འཇོམས་མ།།༡༣

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་ས་གཞིའི་ངོས་ལ་ཕྱག་གོ།
 |མཐིལ་གྱིས་བསྐྱེན་ཅིང་ཞབས་ཀྱིས་བརྟུང་མ།
 |ཁྲི་གཉེར་སྤྱན་མཛད་ཡི་གེ་རྩྱི་གིས།
 |རིམ་པ་བདུན་པོ་རྣམས་ནི་འགེམ་མ།།༡༤

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་བདེ་མ་དགེ་མ་ཞི་མ།
 |མྱ་ངན་འདས་ཞི་སྤྱོད་ཡུལ་ཉིད་མ།
 |སྤྱོད་ལྡོ་ལྡོ་དང་ཡང་དག་ལྡན་མ།
 |སྤྱིག་པ་ཆེན་པོ་འཇོམས་པ་ཉིད་མ།།༡༥

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་ཀུན་ནས་བསྐྱེར་རབ་དགའ་བའི།
 |དབྱ་ཡི་ལུས་ནི་རྣམ་པར་འགེམས་མ།
 |ཡི་གེ་བརྩུ་པའི་ངག་ནི་བཀོད་པ་འི།
 |རིག་པ་རྩྱི་ལས་སྤྱོད་མ་ཉིད་མ།།༡༦

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་དུ་རེ་ཞབས་ནི་བརྟུང་པས།
 |རྩྱི་གི་རྣམ་པའི་ས་བོན་ཉིད་མ།
 |རི་རབ་མཐུ་ར་དང་འབྲིགས་བྱེད།
 |འཇོག་རྟེན་གསུམ་རྣམས་གཡོ་བ་ཉིད་མ།།༡༧

|ཕྱག་འཚལ་ལྷ་ཡི་མཚོ་ཡི་རྣམ་པའི།
 |རི་དྲུགས་རྟུགས་ཅན་ཕྱག་ན་བསྐྱེམས་མ།
 |དུ་ར་གཉེས་བརྗོད་མཁུ་ཀྱི་ཡི་གས།
 |དུག་རྣམས་མ་ལུས་པ་ནི་སེལ་མ།།༡༨

|ཕུག་འཚལ་ལྷ་ཡི་ཚོགས་རྣམས་རྒྱལ་པོ།
 |ལྷ་དང་མི་འམ་ཅི་ཡིས་བསྟེན་མ།
 |ཀུན་ནས་གོ་ཆ་དགའ་བ་བརྗིད་ཀྱིས།
 |ཚེད་དང་མི་ལམ་ངན་པ་སེལ་མ།།༡༩

|ཕུག་འཚལ་ཉི་མ་ལྷ་བ་རྒྱས་པའི།
 |སྤྱན་གཉིས་པོ་ལ་འོད་རབ་གསལ་མ།
 |ཉ་ར་གཉིས་བརྗིད་དུ་རྒྱ་ར་ཡིས།
 |ཤིན་དུ་དྲག་པོའི་རིམས་ནད་སེལ་མ།།༢༠

|ཕུག་འཚལ་དེ་ཉིད་གསུམ་རྣམས་བཀོད་པས།
 |ཞི་བའི་མཐུ་དང་ཡང་དག་ལྷན་མ།
 |གདོན་དང་རོ་ལངས་གཞོད་སྤྱན་ཚོགས་རྣམས།
 |འཛོམས་པ་དུ་རེ་རབ་མཚོག་ཉིད་མ།།༢༡

|ཙ་བའི་ལྷགས་ཀྱིས་བསྟོད་པ་འདི་དང།
 |ཕུག་འཚལ་བ་ནི་ཉི་ལུ་ཙ་གཅིག།

|ཞོ་དུ་རེ་དུ་རྒྱ་རེ་དུ་རེ་སྤྱད། བཀྲ་ཤིས་ཤིག།

TRANSLATION

In the language of India: *Āryatāre mantramūlastottranamaskair ekapiṃśatikanāma*. In
 the language of Tibet: The Eulogy of Root Mantras to Noble Tārā with Twenty
 One Prostrations.

OM. Homage to Tārā, Noble Mother, Honoured Lady.

|1|¹

Homage to you Tārā, heroic mother, swift responder,
whose eyes are like a flash of lightning,
Who is born from the million-petalled bloom
of Avalokiteśvara, lotus-faced lord of the three worlds.

|2|²

Homage to You! Whose tranquil face seems like
a hundred moons, all full and autumal,
Who shines with the wonderfully dazzling light
of a hundred-thousand stars brought altogether.

|3|³

Homage to You! Whose hand is beautifully adorned with a lotus,
water-born in blue and yellow,
You are the very field of spiritual practice for meditation, forbearance,
tranquility, austerity, courageous effort and charity.

|4|⁴

Homage to You! Who heroically employs the immeasurable
crowning knowledge of the Tathāgata,
Who is diligently sought after by the Buddha's spiritual sons,
all of them complete in perfection.

|5|⁵

Homage to You! Who fills space, direction and desire
with the mantras TUTTĀRA and HŪṂ,
Who, pressing down the seven worlds with her foot,
is able to control all beings without exception.

|6|⁶

Homage to You! Who is worshipped by Śakra, Agni,
Brahmā, Vāyu and all kinds of powerful gods,
Who is openly praised by multitudes
of Bhūtas, Vetālas, Gandharvas and Yakṣas.

|7|⁷

Homage to You! Who with the mantras called TRAT and PHAṬ
completely destroys the enemy's magical weapons,
Who, pressing them down with right foot raised and left foot pendant,
blazes ever more gloriously with raging fire.

| 8 |⁸

Homage to You! O Quick One! Great and Terrifying!
Who totally vanquishes the heroes of Mārā,
Who slays every enemy without exception,
by making her lotus-face carry a wrathful frown.

| 9 |⁹

Homage to You! Who beautifully adorns her heart with fingers
in a *mudrā* which symbolises the great Triple Gem,
Who shimmers with many lights all her own,
making a complete, all-enclosing orb.

| 10 |¹⁰

Homage to You! Who radiates a garland of light,
a head ornament which is magnificent and very blissful,
Who overpowers Mārā and Saṃsāra,
by laughing the perfect laugh TUTTĀRA.

| 11 |¹¹

Homage to You! You have the power to summon
every host ruling the world,
You who fully removes every deficiency with the mantra HŪṂ
which wrathfully contorts your brow.

| 12 |¹²

Homage to You! Whose head is decorated with fragments
of the moon, all of which sparkle intensely,
Who generates the best of lights, glorious and eternal, from the
Buddha of limitless light caught up in your matted hair.

| 13 |¹³

Homage to You! Who resides in the middle of a blazing garland
which is like the conflagration at the end of time,
Who, with right foot pendant and left foot raised,
Smashes great enemy forces circling round on all sides.

| 14 |¹⁴

Homage to You! Who presses down the earth's surface
with the palm of her hand and drubs it with her foot,
Who shatters the seven underworlds with the mantra HŪṂ

which springs from a wrathful flicker in her eyes.

| 15 |¹⁵

Homage to You! You are well-being, virtue and peace,
You are the field of practice for the peace of *nirvāṇa*,
You are the one who overpowers great evil,
endowed with the sublime mantras OM and SVĀHA.

| 16 |¹⁶

Homage to You! Who utterly destroys enemies incarnate,
who circle all round in happy abundance,
You are the one who springs from the wisdom mantra HŪM,
produced from the words of your ten-syllabled sound.

| 17 |

Homage to You! O Quick One! By stomping with your foot
You are the source of HŪM's aspects,
You are the shaker of the three worlds,
the mountains Vindhya, Mandara and Sumeru.

| 18 |¹⁷

Homage to You! Who in her hand holds the deer-marked moon
like the ocean of the gods,
Who cures all poisons without exception
with the mantra of PHAṬ, uttering TĀRA twice.

| 19 |

Homage to You! Who is relied upon by the king
of the heavenly hosts, the gods and the kinnaras,
Who dispells bad dreams and disputes
with the joyous lustre of her armour.

| 20 |

Homage to You! The radiant light in whose eyes
is like the sun and moon in full glory,
Who removes very severe plagues
with the mantra TUTTĀRA, uttering HARA twice.

| 21 |¹⁸

Homage to You! Possessed of power and of tranquility,
made by setting down the three essential truths,
You are the destroyer of hordes of Yakṣas, Vetālas, and Grahas.

O Quick One! You are ever so great!

This is the eulogy made of root mantras with one and twenty prostrations.

OM TĀRE TUTTĀRE TURE SVĀHĀ. May there be good fortune!

The text in question has been the subject of western scholarship since the nineteenth century. Wadell made a translation from the Tibetan.¹⁹ The text also survives in Sanskrit and an edition was published by Godefroy de Blonay in 1895.²⁰

Wayman made an attempt to synthesise the Sanskrit versions based on the Kanjur version and those provided by de Blonay but his reading in some cases do not advance the study of this text.²¹

namastārāyai

namas tāre ture vīre kṣaṇair dyutinibhekṣaṇe |
trailokyanāthavaktrābjavikasatkesarodbhave || 1

namaḥ śataśaraccandrasaṃpūrṇapaṭālānane |
tārāsahasranikaraprahasatkiraṇojjvale || 2

namaḥ kanakanīlābijapāṇipadmavidbhuṣite |
dānavīryatapaḥ śāntitikṣādhyānagocare || 3

namas tathāgatoṣṇīṣavijayānantacāriṇi |
śeṣapāramitāprāptajinaputraniṣevite || 4

namas tuttārehūṃkārāpūritāśādigntare |
saptalokakramākrānti niḥśeṣākarsaṇakṣame || 5

namaḥ śakrānalabrahmarudviśveśvarārcite |
bhūtavetālagandharvagaṇayakṣapuraskṛte || 6

namas traḍitiphaṭkārāparayantrapramardini |
pratyālīḍhpadanyāse śikhijvalākulekṣaṇe || 7

namas ture mahāghore mārāvīravīnāśini |
bhṛkuṭīkṛtavaktrābjasarvaśatruniṣūdini || 8

namas triratnamudrāṅkahṛdyāṅgulivibhūṣite |
bhūṣitāśeṣadikcakranikarasvakarākule || 9

namaḥ pramuditāṭopamukuṭākṣiptamālinī |
hasatprahasattuttāremāralokavaśaṃkari || 10

namaḥ samantabhūpālapaṭalākarṣaṇakṣame |
caladbhṛkuṭīhūṃkārasarvāpadavimocinī || 11

namaḥ śikhaṇḍakhaṇḍendumukuṭābharaṇojjvale |
amitābhajaṭābhārabhāsvarakiraṇadhruve || 12

namaḥ kalpāntahutabhugjvālamāntarasthite |
ālīḍhamuditābaddharipucakravinaśīni || 13

namaḥ karatalāghātacaraṇāhatabhūtale |
bhṛkuṭīkṛtahūṃkārasaptapātālabhedini || 14

namaḥ śive śubhe śānte śāntanirvāṇagocare |
svāhāpraṇavasamṃyukte mahāpāpakanāśīni || 15

namaḥ pramuditābaddharipugātraprabhedini |
daśākṣarapadanyāsavidyāhūṃkāradīpīte || 16

namas turepādāghāte hūṃkāṛākārabijite |
merumandārakailāsabhuvanatrayacālīni || 17

namas surasarākārahariṇāṅkakarasthite |
tāradviruktaphaṭkāra²² aśeṣaviṣanāśīni || 18

namaḥ suragaṇādhyakṣasurakiṃnarasevite |
ābaddhamuditābhogakaliduḥsvapnanāśīni || 19

namaścandrārkasaṃpūrṇanayanadyutibhāsure |
haradviruktatuttāreviṣamajvaranāśīni || 20

namas tritatāvinyāsaśivaśaktisamanvite |
grahavetālayakṣagaṇanāśāni pravare ture || 21

mantramūlam idaṃ stotraṃ namaskāraikaviṃśakaṃ |

yaḥ paṭhetprasannadhīmān devyāṃ bhaktisamanvitaḥ | | 22

sāyaṃ vā prātarutthāya smaretsarvābhaya-pradaṃ |
sarvapāpaprāśamaṃ sarvadurgatināśanaṃ | | 23

abhiṣikto bhavettūrṇaṃ saptabhir jinakoṭibhiḥ
asmin mahattvamāpadya so'ante bauddhapadaṃ vrajet | | 24

viṣaṃ tasya mahāghoraṃ sthāvaram vātha jaṅgamaṃ |
smaraṇāt pralayaṃ yāti khāditam pītam eva vā | | 25

grahajvaraviṣārtināṃ paramārtivināśānāṃ |
anyeṣāṃ caiva sattvānāṃ dvitrisaptābhivarttināṃ | | 26

putrakāmo labhet putraṃ dhanakāmo labheddhanam |
sarvakāmānavāpnoti na vidhnaiḥ pratihanyate | | 27

samyak sambuddhabhāṣitaṃ bhagavatītārādevyāṃ namaskāraikaviśatistotraṃ
guṇahitasahitaṃ saṃpūram samāptaṃ | tāre svāhā | |

¹ This verse gives a cryptic description of Tārā as born in lotuses which grew in the pools created by Avalokiteśvara's tears of compassion. The reference here in the opening verse indicates that the myth enjoyed wide currency in the eleventh century. Tārā is called *सुखी* not because she is swift per se, but because she responds swiftly to those in need, thus the translation offered; see further comments to verse 8.

² The somewhat problematic *समस्त* in this verse Beyer, *Cult of Tārā*, p. 212, renders 'with laughing beams' which I do not find here. The verb means basically 'to open, divide, distinguish, differentiate'. My guess is that the light about the goddess shines or blazes like innumerable stars, but that these lights are nonetheless differentiated or kept apart; in contrast the face of Tārā in the first part of the verse is likened to hundreds of moons piled up together; I have added 'tranquil', not in the original but a quality inherent in the Indic conception of the moon.

³ In this verse the goddess is visualised holding a lotus, a typical attitude in many representations. The lotus is described as blue and yellow: two-tone flowers appear often in paintings although not always in these two specific colours. The second part of the verse turns to the six *pāramitā*-s: *dhyāna* *བསམ་གཏན་*, *kṣanti* *བརྗོད་པ་*, *śānti* *ཞིབ་*, *tapasyā* *དགའ་ཐུབ་*, *vīrya* *བརྗོད་འགྲུས་*, *dāna* *བྱིན་པ་*. Tārā is described as the field (*viṣaya*) in which these are practiced, i. e. she is not what the perfections are applied to achieve but rather in whom they are, with her grace, successfully performed.

⁴ The first half of this verse literally states that Tārā participates in the total victory of the *uṣṇīṣa*, the cranial protuberance on the Buddha's head. So one might visualise an image

of the Buddha with a small figure of Tārā mounted there. While this should not be ruled out, the verb has a more active sense and the *uṣṇīṣa* is an attribute indicative of the Buddha's higher spiritual knowledge.

⁵ The words 'space, direction and desire' refer to the three realms or *traidhātu*, i.e. *kāma*, *rūpa* and *arūpa*. See 2003.7-3.06 where the term *त्रिसन्निवेश* is actually used.

⁶ The description given here may refer to a visualisation in which the goddess is surrounded by various beings, the divine ones appearing above, the demonic ones below. The term *समुन्मुख* is literally 'from the front' and could refer to a spacial position as one might see in a picture but here I suspect it means in 'an open fashion'; colloquially speaking the demons are 'up front' in their praise. The *yakṣa*-s in Tibet (གནོད་ལྗེ་) are 'harm-givers' understood to be powerful mountain spirits who need to be placated lest they bring harm to travellers. This helps explain why prayer-flags with this text are raised on mountain passes. The importance of Tārā's power over *yakṣa*-s and other evil forces is brought out again in the closing verse of this text.

⁷ The description here refers to the so-called *lalitāsana* in which one foot is tucked up and the other hangs down, a frequent way of depicting Tārā in sculpture and painting; see again verse 13. Here the verb, already used in verse 5, *सदक* pf. and ft. of *चक्र* 'to press down, suppress (ritually)' is the same used to describe the 'district-subduing temples'; the Tārā hymn thus has points of thematic contact with more standard prayer-flag texts; see further Introduction, pp. 000. The reference to 'magical wheels of enemies' as well as the concern with control and regulation in many of the verses shows this text touches the orb of mediaeval *Dhanurveda*, see University of Madras, Sanskrit Department, *New Catalogus Catalogorum: An Alphabetical Register of Sanskrit and Allied Works and Authors* (Madras, 1968-on) 9: 224-25 to which add Devavrata Acarya, *Dhanurveda* (Delhi, 1998). The subject is not supported by a well-developed secondary literature but as a start see Daud Ali, 'Violence, Gastronomy and the Meanings of War in Medieval South India', *Medieval History Journal* 3 (2001): 261-89.

⁸ The syntax of this verse provides some interesting problems. The word *ture* is Sanskrit and generally understood as a *mantra*, and indeed appears in the celebrated ten-syllabled *mantra* of Tārā which closes this selection. But *mantra*-s are typically in the vocative case and this one is based on the word *tara*, 'quick, ready, willing'. In the opening verse Tārā is described as *सुत* 'speedy' so I think we can understand this as a Sanskrit vocative in the poem itself; the same appears again verses 17 and 21.

⁹ Beyer, *Cult of Tārā*, p. 212 gives 'her palms adorned with the universal wheel radiating a turbulent host of its own beams'. The description would appear to be more technical and precise. Tārā does indeed show her palm raised at her breast, but the word 'palm' is not actually used and the palms are not, in the pictures I have seen, adorned with *cakra*-s. Rather they have little eyes, as in the prayer-flag image illustrated here. The last line is anyway clear: Tārā shimmers or pulsates with many lights which are her own, i.e. the radiance is self-effulgent. Now this light is 'ornamented' (*सुशोभ*). I would take this as representing Skt *alamkāra*, and translate somewhat archaically 'make or making complete'. On this matter see A. K. Coomaraswamy, 'Ornamant', *Art Bulletin* 21 (1939): 375-82; J. Gonda, 'The Meaning of the Word Alamkāra', *Selected Studies* 2: 257-74. Finally there is the qualifying phrase *सर्वदिक्* 'This is not so much 'universal' but 'all directions

without a gap (*nikhila*). The print again helps: the whole image is neatly encircled with an unbroken circle or outer orb; in coloured pictures the space between this and the inner halo is often painted with little flames.

¹⁰ The last verse introduced the outer orb, now we have the small halo around the head, see figure **000**.

¹¹ The *mantra* HŪṂ is closely related to the wrathful grimace of the goddess's brow, also in verse 14.

¹² Another verse bringing the light of the celestial bodies together with Tārā. The theme was introduced in verse 2 and reappears in verse 20. Here the 'pieces or chunks of the moon' would seem to be the jewels that are inserted as decorations in Tārā's crown. The 'Buddha of limitless light' is Amitābha, the description referring to the small figure that is sometime placed in Tārā's hair like an amulet.

¹³ In this verse there is another description of the mandorla, a subject first taken up in verses 9-10. As already mentioned, the haloes often contain a flame-like design. The position of the feet is reversed compared to verse 7: images frequently show one or other of the legs up and the other down, an arrangement which, like hand-gestures, evidently had special meanings. Here the word དགའི་ is slightly problematic; it means 'joyous' or 'happy' and qualifies the enemy hosts, the implication perhaps being that the enemies revel in their destruction and thus in their escape from demonic bodies. But I am not sure this is right. A close phrase appears in verse 16 where the poem reads བཞུམས་ཀྱི་རྒྱ་ནག་བཟོར་འབྱོར་ དགའ་བའི་དགའ་ལྷན་. This recalls དགའ་འབྱོར་ used adjectivally to describe a great mass or happy abundance; so our word could be a Tibetan rendering of the Sanskrit *subhojah*.

¹⁴ The phrase རེ་མཉམ་པ་བདུན་པོ་རྒྱུ་སྤྱོད་ literally means the seven layers or levels; here I follow the suggestion of Beyer, *Cult of Tārā*, p. 213.

¹⁵ As in verse 3, Tārā is described as the domain in which spiritual practice takes place. The words དང་ཡང་དག་ལྷན་ appears again in verse 21 where the meaning of the phrase is taken up.

¹⁶ For the understanding of 'abundance' see comments on verse 13. In the second half of the verse, the 'ten *akṣara-s*' are the syllables in Tārā's *mantra* OṂ TĀRE TUTTĀRE TURE SVĀHĀ; I understand བཞོན་པ་ as *samāhita-*, 'placed, conceived or established in; produced from'.

¹⁷ The reference to saying a *mantra* twice appears again in verse 20. For ocean of gods, see ramachandra inscription** [endnote]

¹⁸ The phrase དང་ཡང་དག་ལྷན་ also appears in verse 15. From the modern perspective the meaning is 'fully endowed with the power of tranquility', but I prefer a more difficult path taking དག་ as signalling a Sanskrit dual ending, thus 'possessed of power and of tranquility as well'. Beyer, *Cult of Tārā*, p. 213 explains the three *tattva-s* as OṂ, ĀḤ and HŪṂ.

¹⁹ L. A. Wadell, 'The Indian Buddhist Cult of Avalokita and his Consort Tārā 'the Saviouress', illustrated from the Remains in Magadha', *JRAS* (1894): 71-4.

²⁰ Godefroy de Blony, *Matériaux pour servir à l'histoire de la déesse buddhique* (Paris, 1895).

²¹ Wayman, 'The Twenty-one Praises of Tārā, a Syncretism of Śaivism and Buddhism' in *Buddhist Insight* (Delhi, 1984): 441- 47.

²² Wayman ammends the text phaṭkārair aśeṣa.